

Interstellar knowledge dynamics

Lai Kwun Hang^[0000–0003–0446–119X]

Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University,
`k.h.lai@cwts.leidenuniv.nl`

Abstract. Knowledge has always been an important cornerstone of our civilization, and we believe this will continue to be true for our future interstellar society. In this study, we construct an interstellar knowledge dynamics model, which allows us to explore how innovations would look like in a social system subjected to special relativity. Our simulation results illustrate some interesting insights on how speed of light, distance-based cooperation selection strategies, and movement strategies, are going to affect the efficiencies and rewards of the social system. The implementation is available at <https://github.com/Adriankhl/relativitization-model-knowledge-dynamics>.

Keywords: agent based model, knowledge diffusion, interstellar society, special relativity

1 Introduction

Scientific development is a major driver of our society. There are many ways to study scientific development. On the more theoretical side, philosophers dive deep into the fundamental definition of “scientific progress” [14]. On the more practical side, one can study the sociological aspect of innovations, such as modeling and measuring innovation diffusion networks [2, 11, 19, 12, 17]. Recent developments have gone beyond simple diffusion processes to address the more fundamental nature of knowledge, introducing addition mechanisms such as self-learning [17], perception of knowledge value [10], and network representation of knowledge [15]. However, extending network models greatly complexifies the underlying mathematics, making it not easy to explore more complicated knowledge dynamics.

Alternatively, agent based modeling (ABM) can be used to model knowledge dynamics. ABM allows scholars to explore complicated knowledge dynamics models without dealing with mathematical subtleties. While it remains to be a challenge to calibrate and validate the model, many ABMs have been created to study innovation diffusion [18]. Particularly, we are interested in the family of *simulating knowledge dynamics in innovation networks* (SKIN) models [1]. Inspired by how neo-Schumpeterian economics theorizes innovations [7], SKIN models feature the *kene* representation of knowledge. Agents can research to update their *kenes*, form collaboration to exchange *kenes*, and produce outputs based on their *kenes*. Different SKIN models have been applied to study many hypothetical scenerios as well as real-world scenerios [4].

In this study, we extend the idea of SKIN models to create an agent based model to investigate the knowledge dynamics of our distant future - when human society become interstellar. The model is built on top of the *Relativitization* framework [9, 8], which helps to take care of the effects of relativistic physics in interstellar social simulation. The model allow us to explore how relativistic effects, such as time delay, time dilation, relativistic movement, affect the pattern of knowledge creation, cooperation, and diffusion in interstellar societies. Particularly, we will simulate the model to demonstrate the impact of speed of light, distance-based cooperators selection strategy, and agents movement, on the efficiency and reward of the innovation system.

2 Definition

2.1 Special relativity

Based on the observation that the laws of physics and the speed of light are invariant for all inertial observers, Einstein proposed the theory of special relativity [3]. The verification of special relativity (see [6] for some examples of experiments) had drastically changed our understanding of the universe. In the context of ABM, if we want to construct an interstellar model, we at least have to consider the followings [8]:

- **time delay**: everything cannot travel faster than the speed of light c , and information travels at the speed of light, so agents can only see the past of other agents,
- **time dilation**: clock of a moving object ticks slower, so time-consuming mechanisms of an agent process slower if the agent is moving.

2.2 Kene

A *kene* is represented by a triple $K = (C, A, E)$, where capability C is a field of the knowledge, ability A is a specific topic/skill of that field, and expertise E is the competence level for this specific *kene* [5]. As an example, (computer science - topic modeling - expert) is a *kene*, an agent who owned this kene is an expert in computer science working on topic modeling. The set of possible kenes depends on the specific research context. Since our model is created for exploring general patterns, we use *kene* in a general sense, where C , A and E are represented by integers from 0 to C_{\max} , A_{\max} and E_{\max} respectively.

An agent i can possess multiple *kenes*. We define the knowledge base of agent i as a set of *kenes*

$$\{ K_{ik} \mid k \text{ is an integer} \}. \quad (1)$$

2.3 Cooperator

In our model, knowledge diffusion is driven by cooperators. Whenever agent i wants to have agent j as a cooperator:

1. agent i sends an invitation to agent j , the potential cooperation appears on the waitlist of agent i ,
2. after a time delay (see Sec. 2.1), agent j receives the invitation and confirms the cooperation,
3. after another time delay, agent i notices that agent j has confirmed the cooperation, the cooperation leaves the waitlist of agent i and becomes an actual cooperation,
4. after a fixed time $t_{\text{cooperation}}$, the cooperation ends, and agent i learns some knowledge from agent j (see Sec. 3.5).

We call this an out-cooperation of agent i and an in-cooperation of agent j .

3 Simulation model

In a simulation, n_{agent} agents are placed uniformly and randomly into a world with 3 spacial dimensions of size $X_{\text{max}} \times Y_{\text{max}} \times Z_{\text{max}}$. During a simulation step, an agent undergoes movement (Sec. 3.1), cooperator selection (Sec. 3.2), innovation hypothesis output (Sec. 3.3), reward (Sec. 3.4), and knowledge dynamics (Sec. 3.5). All mechanisms beside movement are time consuming so they are subject to time dilation. These mechanisms are called dilated mechanisms in the simulation framework, see [8] for more details.

3.1 Movement

Because the time delay between agents plays an important role in our model, and the time delay depends on the distance between agents, we allow agents to move. We assume agent i has an intrinsic speed v_i , where $v_i < c$. In the real world, it is not uncommon to have a very attractive location for researchers, e.g., an institute with good reputation, such that all researchers try to migrate to that specific location to do research. In this model, we assume that such an attractive location $(X_{\text{target}}, Y_{\text{target}}, Z_{\text{target}})$ exist, and all agents move towards the location at their own speed and stop there. Under this simple rule, agents become closer to each other as time goes on. The movement reduces the time delay, but it also generates the time dilation effect, which can create interesting observations.

3.2 Cooperator selection

Depending on the state of an agent (see Sec. 3.5), it may decide to find a new cooperator based on a strategy. Because the distance between agents is one of our core interests, we are interested in exploring the consequence of distance-based cooperator selection strategies. When agent i decided to find a new cooperator, it scan through the list of other agents in its view, then compute the distance d_{ij} between itself and agent j for each agent j in the list (technically speaking, the distance is the spatial distance of the integer coordinates, see [8] for a detailed

description). The probability of agent j to be selected as the new cooperator is proportional to

$$\frac{1}{1 + d_{ij}^{\delta_i}}, \quad (2)$$

where δ_i is a non-negative number to control the distance preference for the new cooperator - larger δ_i implies that agent i prefers closer agents as cooperators, and $\delta_i = 0$ means the selection is purely random.

3.3 Innovation hypothesis output

An innovation hypothesis is a subset of the knowledge base selected by an agent. After selecting an innovation hypothesis, the agent can produce an output, e.g., manufacture a product for sale, to receive an reward. The output from an agent has two attributes - type and quality. The type of the output determines the competitive pressure the agent faced: the more output of the same type from other agents, the more competitive the market. The quality of the output determines whether the agent can outcompete other agents to receive more reward.

Our model follows the setting of Matthias et al. [13]. Let

$$I_i = \{k \mid K_{ik} \text{ belongs to the innovation hypothesis of agent } i\}. \quad (3)$$

The size of innovation hypothesis is the same for all agents, so $|I_i| = n_{\text{hypothesis}}$ where $n_{\text{hypothesis}}$ is an integer.

The type of output is represented as an integer. To mimic the randomness of output type by different combinations of *kene*, the type is computed as

$$\left(\sum_{k \in I_i} C_{ik} \right) \bmod n_{\text{type}}, \quad (4)$$

where n_{type} is the total number of output types. Only agents with the same output type compete with each other.

The quality of output is decomposed into three factors: capability factor f_i^C , ability factor f_i^A , and expertise factor f_i^E .

$$f_i^C = \frac{\sum_{k \in I_i} C_{ik}}{n_{\text{hypothesis}} C_{\max}}, \quad (5)$$

$$f_i^A = \frac{(\sum_{k \in I_i} A_{ik}) \bmod (A_{\max} + 1)}{A_{\max}}, \quad (6)$$

$$f_i^E = \frac{\sum_{k \in I_i} E_{ik}}{n_{\text{hypothesis}} E_{\max}}. \quad (7)$$

Every *kene* in the innovation hypothesis has an influence to the quality of the output, f_i^C is constructed to have a variety of qualities with the same output type because of Eq. 4, where larger capacities give better qualities, f_i^A mimics

the randomness of quality by different combinations of *kenes*, and f_i^E represents that the quality of the output correlates to the average expertise of all the *kenes* in the innovation hypothesis.

The overall quality of the output is computed as:

$$f_i^C \cdot f_i^A \cdot f_i^E \cdot n_{\text{quality}}, \quad (8)$$

where n_{quality} is the maximum possible quality of output.

3.4 Reward

In a realistic market, the interactions between buyers and sellers determine the price and thus the profit of a product. In our model, to simplify the implementation, there is no buy/sell process, rewards depend solely on the output qualities within the same type:

1. agent i retrieves a list of outputs from other agents, note that “other agents” mean the state of other agents as seen by agent i , which is affected by relativistic effects,
2. from the list of outputs, filter out outputs that is not of the same type as the output of agent i ,
3. the remaining outputs are shuffled and sorted by qualities in descending order,
4. say the output quality of agent i is at the j position (count from 0) of the list, agent i receives $\max(n_{\text{reward}} - j, 0)$ amount of reward, where n_{reward} is a positive integer.

3.5 Knowledge dynamics

Because of “learning by doing” [16], the expertise E_{ik} of every *kene* in the innovation hypothesis of agent i increases by 1 until it reaches E_{max} . In contrast, the expertise of every other *kene* in the knowledge base of every agent decreases by 1 until it reaches 0. If the expertise of any *kene* is 0, there is a probability p_{forget} where the agent forgets this *kene*.

There are 2 key thresholds of rewards, incremental threshold $n_{\text{incremental}}$ and radical threshold n_{radical} , where $n_{\text{reward}} \geq n_{\text{incremental}} \geq n_{\text{radical}} \geq 0$. When the reward of an agent is larger than $n_{\text{incremental}}$, the agent is happy about the situation and does nothing. When the reward of an agent is between $n_{\text{incremental}}$ (inclusive) and n_{radical} (exclusive), the agent undergoes incremental changes. When the reward of an agent is not larger than n_{radical} , the agent undergoes radical changes.

If agent i undergoes incremental changes, it does self-incremental innovation with a probability $p_{\text{self-incremental}}$, and always does incremental knowledge diffusion:

- self-incremental innovation: randomly pick a *kene* in the innovation hypothesis and randomly change the ability A_{ik} of the *kene* to a new ability between 0 and A_{\max} ,
- incremental knowledge diffusion: for each agent j who just ended the cooperation with agent i , randomly select (if exists) a *kene* $K_{jk'}$ from the innovation hypothesis of agent j where there is a *kene* K_{ik} in the innovation hypothesis of agent i with the same capacity, i.e., $C_{jk'} = C_{ik}$, then replace A_{ik} by $A_{jk'}$.

The overall new innovation hypothesis is the old innovation hypothesis with abilities changed in some *kenes*. The output type of agent i remains the same, and the quality of the output may increase or decrease, depends on the new abilities and Eq.6.

If agent i undergoes radical changes, it does self-radical innovation with a probability $p_{\text{self-radical}}$, always does radical knowledge diffusion, and follows by *kene*-replacement,

- self-radical innovation: add a new *kene* K_{ik} to the knowledge base where C_{ik} is a random integer between 0 and C_{\max} , A_{ik} is a random integer between 0 and A_{\max} , and $E_{ik} = 0$,
- radical knowledge diffusion: for each agent j who just ended the cooperation with agent i , randomly copy a *kene* $K_{jk'}$ from the innovation hypothesis of agent j , set the expertise $E_{jk'}$ of the copied *kene* to 0, then add this *kene* to the knowledge base of agent i ,
- *kene*-replacement: if there exists some *kenes* in the knowledge base of agent i that is not in its innovation hypothesis, randomly replace one *kene* in the innovation hypothesis by another *kene* that is not in the innovation hypothesis.

The overall new innovation hypothesis may have a completely new *kene*, which means the type and the quality of the output of agent i may both change, depends on the new *kene* and Eqs. 4-8.

Additionally, seeking new cooperators is also a way of making changes. In this model the number of out-cooperation is limited because we assume that seeking cooperation actively is a much more time-consuming activities than accepting a cooperation. If agent i undergoes incremental changes or radical changes, and if the number of existing out-cooperation (including those in the waitlist) is smaller than an integer $n_{\text{max-cooperation}}$, agent i will find a new cooperator in the next turn (see Sec. 2.3).

4 Simulation result

There are 3 core variables in our studies: speed of light, cooperator selection strategies, and agent movement. If we set the speed of light to infinity, our model becomes a normal model in a normal world without relativistic effects. Therefore, in Sec. 4.2, we assume random cooperator selection and disable agent movement to explore the effect of speed of light. Then, in Sec. 4.3, we explore how distance preferences of cooperators affect the simulation results. In

Sec. 4.4, we turn on agent movement to see the impact of distances between agents and time dilation. The implementation is available at <https://github.com/Adriankhl/relativitization-model-knowledge-dynamics>.

4.1 Parameters and initialization

Parameters in Table 1 determine how the simulated world is initialized. Additionally, when an agent is initialized, it receives 3 random *kenes* to its knowledge base, and the random *kenes* are added to its innovation hypothesis immediately. The capability C_{ik} of the random *kene* is a random integer between 0 and 30. Since 30 is smaller than C_{\max} , there are space reserved for improving qualities of agent outputs (see Eq.5). The ability A_{ik} of the *kene* is an integer between 0 and A_{\max} , and the expertise E_{ik} of the *kene* is 0.

Parameter	value	Parameter	value
X_{\max}	10	$n_{\text{hypothesis}}$	3
Y_{\max}	10	C_{\max}	100
Z_{\max}	10	A_{\max}	10
X_{target}	10	E_{\max}	20
Y_{target}	10	c	?
Z_{target}	10	p_{forget}	?
n_{agent}	100	$p_{\text{self-incremental}}$?
n_{type}	50	$p_{\text{self-radical}}$?
n_{quality}	50	$t_{\text{cooperation}}$?
n_{reward}	10	$n_{\text{max-cooperation}}$?
$n_{\text{incremental}}$	8	v_i	?
n_{radical}	6	δ_i	?

Table 1: Simulation parameters. Some parameters are fixed throughout this study, parameters with ? value depend the specific simulation.

4.2 Speed of light effects

We set $p_{\text{forget}} = 0.05$, $p_{\text{self-incremental}} = 0.1$, $p_{\text{self-radical}} = 0.4$, $t_{\text{cooperation}} = 5$, and $n_{\text{max-cooperation}} = \infty$. Furthermore, $v_i = 0$ and $\delta_i = 0$ for every agent i . Then, we run 4 sets of simulations with $c \in \{0.1, 1.0, 10.0, 200.0\}$, in each set of simulations there are 10 runs with different random seeds.

Fig. 1 summarizes the simulated output qualities and rewards. Interestingly, while the output quality improves slower in a world with a slower speed of light initially, the output quality will surpass other worlds with faster speeds of light eventually. The initial quality difference is driven by the knowledge diffusion, the faster the speed of light, the faster the knowledge diffusion rate, so the quality improves faster. However, because the reward is calculated by “comparison” (see

Sec. 3.4), a faster information travel speed means an agent is comparing itself with latest state of other agents, it is more competitive and receives a lower reward in average. Therefore, a faster speed of light also causes agents to become less likely to develop the expertise in their *kenes*. This is illustrated in Fig. 2, the capability factor is higher if the speed of light is higher, but the expertise factor is lower. Because the amount of knowledge (number of possible *kenes*) is limited in our model, as long as the rate of new knowledge discovery slows down, reflected in the slower increase of capability factor, the expertise factor is the deterministic factor of the overall quality and a slower speed of light is beneficial to the output quality.

Fig. 1: (left) Output qualities improve with time, simulated worlds with slower speed of light start with slower quality improvement rates but catch up and surpass later on. (right) Rewards are higher for simulated worlds with slower speed of light.

Fig. 2: (left) worlds with faster speed of light have higher capability factors. (right) worlds with slower speed of light have higher expertise factors.

4.3 Cooperator distance preference effects

In this section, we fix $c = 0.5$, $v_i = 0$ and vary δ_i to investigate the impact of distance preferences of new cooperators. To focus on the effect of cooperation, we increase p_{forget} to 0.5 to reduce the impact of old knowledge base, decrease $p_{\text{self-incremental}}$ to 0.1 and $p_{\text{self-radical}}$ to 0.02 to reduce the impact of self innovation. We also reduce $t_{\text{cooperation}}$ to 1 and $n_{\text{max-cooperation}}$ to 1 so that the choice of the only cooperator is important.

Fig. 3 shows the output qualities and rewards of 3 sets of simulation with $\delta_i \in \{0.0, 10.0\}$, where each set consists of 10 simulations with different random seeds. Since larger δ_i implies that the cooperation distances are smaller in average, there are more knowledge diffusions so the output qualities improve faster. Unlike Sec. 4.2, this does not significantly change the competition pressure so we always see larger higher qualities for larger δ_i . The reward pattern is not too interesting in these simulations. To see the impact of δ_i on rewards, we run another 50 simulations with different random seeds where 34 agents with $\delta_i = 0.0$, 34 agents with $\delta_i = 0.5$, and 32 agents with $\delta_i = 10.0$ compete with each other in the same simulated world, as illustrated in Fig. 4. Agents with larger δ_i outperform agents with smaller δ_i in both output qualities and rewards because they undergo more knowledge diffusions.

Fig. 3: (left) Output qualities improve with time, closer cooperations (larger δ_i) improve the qualities faster. (right) Rewards remain similar regardless of the cooperation distance preference.

4.4 Agent movement effects

For the simulation in this section, we are interested in the effects of agent movement. Movement introduces two effects: (1) because of how we design the movement (see Sec. 3.1), moving agents keep getting closer to each other, (2) moving agents experience time dilation, so everything, e.g., production, receiving reward, is slower. We fix $c = 1.0$. We keep $p_{\text{forget}} = 0.5$, $p_{\text{self-incremental}} = 0.1$ and

Fig. 4: (left) Agents who prefer closer cooperators (larger δ_i) improve the qualities faster. (right) Agents who prefer closer cooperators (larger δ_i) outcomplete agents who prefer farther cooperators (smaller δ_i).

$p_{\text{self-radical}} = 0.02$. To give agents who move closer to each other an advantage we set $\delta_i = 10$, $t_{\text{cooperation}} = 10$ and $n_{\text{max-cooperation}} = 10$ so those agents can find closer cooperators.

We run a set of 20 simulation with different random seeds, in each simulation, half of the agent (50) moves at $v_i = 0.9c$ and the other half (50) stand still ($v_i = 0$). The simulation result is show in Fig. 5. Initially, moving agents receive fewer rewards because they experience time dilation. After the moving agents arrive coordinate $(0, 0, 0)$ and stop there, they can set up close by cooperations so they undergo more knowledge diffusions and start to outperform non-moving agents.

Fig. 5: (left) Moving agents lack behind initially in cumulative rewards but it pays off later on. (right) the same plot as the (left) plot but the trend is clearer by subtracting the average reward of agents with $v_i = 0$.

5 Discussion

We have constructed an interstellar knowledge dynamics model based on the SKIN framework. The simulations illustrated some interesting results: a world with a slower speed of light starts worse but reaches a higher average product quality eventually, agents who prefer closer cooperators have a better performance, and agents who move closer to each other perform worst but outcompete other agents later on. These results give us some insights on how knowledge dynamics work in interstellar societies.

While this is a hypothetical scenario where realism cannot be judged easily, we can still criticize our model sensibly. One of the biggest issues of the model is how the reward is calculated. As described in Sec. 3.4, the reward is computed by “comparison”. This makes sense in a market with no time delay, since one can argue that if you have a product with better quality, you can expect a higher profit. However, since we have introduced time delay in our simulation, the total reward is no longer a fixed number as it can depend on the time delay, as what we have found in Sec. 4.2. While we can interpret this reward as the overall welfare of the people, a more realistic reward system may help to unveil how an interstellar market actually works.

The relativistic effect we considered in this study - time delay and time dilation, might find their relevance in the “real world” which is not (yet) interstellar. For example, there is always a delay when information diffuses in a network, so our results related to time-delay in Sec. 4.2 and Sec. 4.3 may also give some insight to “real world” problems, i.e., slower information diffusion rate may benefit the society in the long term, and people in the real world may want to prioritize closer cooperators. The time dilation in this model essentially associates a cost to agent movement, which is also not uncommon in the “real world”, where people might have to make the decision between taking efforts to move to a better city (with closer cooperators) and staying at the current place. Sec. 4.4 might teach us something about these “real world” mobility problems, where moving to a better place pays off in the long term.

While the model is not fully realistic and it cannot be verified in the near future, this study shows that simulations can be used to explore our interstellar future scientifically.

References

1. P. Ahrweiler, A. Pyka, and N. Gilbert: Simulating knowledge dynamics in innovation networks (SKIN). In: *Industry and labor dynamics: The agent-based computational economics approach*, pp. 284–296. World Scientific (2004)
2. R. Cowan: *Network models of innovation and knowledge diffusion. Clusters, networks and innovation* (2005)
3. A. Einstein *et al.*: On the electrodynamics of moving bodies. *Annalen der Physik* 17(10), 891–921 (1905)
4. N. Gilbert, P. Ahrweiler, A. Pyka, *et al.*: *Simulating knowledge dynamics in innovation networks*. Springer (2014)

5. N. Gilbert, A. Pyka, P. Ahrweiler, *et al.*: Innovation networks—a simulation approach. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation* 4(3), 1–13 (2001)
6. G. Gwinner: Experimental tests of time dilation in special relativity. *Modern Physics Letters A* 20(11), 791–805 (2005)
7. H. Hanusch and A. Pyka: Principles of neo-Schumpeterian economics. *Cambridge Journal of Economics* 31(2), 275–289 (2007)
8. K.H. Lai: On social simulation in 4D relativistic spacetime. arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.11019 (2022)
9. MISC
10. S.-G. Liao and S.-P. Yi: Modeling and dynamic analysis of knowledge transmission process: A model considering individual perception of knowledge value. *Communications in Nonlinear Science and Numerical Simulation* 95, 105598 (2021)
11. N. Meade and T. Islam: Modelling and forecasting the diffusion of innovation—A 25-year review. *International Journal of forecasting* 22(3), 519–545 (2006)
12. A. Melo, C.L. Beck, J.I. Peña, and P.E. Paré: Knowledge transfer from universities to regions as a network spreading process. In: 2018 IEEE International Systems Engineering Symposium (ISSE), pp. 1–8 (2018)
13. M. Mueller, T. Buchmann, and M. Kudic: Micro strategies and macro patterns in the evolution of innovation networks: an agent-based simulation approach. In: *Simulating knowledge dynamics in innovation networks*, pp. 73–95. Springer (2014)
14. I. Niiniluoto: Scientific Progress. *Synthese* 45(3), 427–462 (1980)
15. M.P. Schlaile, J. Zeman, and M. Mueller: It’s a match! Simulating compatibility-based learning in a network of networks. In: *Memetics and Evolutionary Economics*, pp. 99–140. Springer (2021)
16. P. Thompson: Learning by doing. *Handbook of the Economics of Innovation* 1, 429–476 (2010)
17. H. Wang, J. Wang, L. Ding, and W. Wei: Knowledge transmission model with consideration of self-learning mechanism in complex networks. *Applied Mathematics and Computation* 304, 83–92 (2017)
18. H. Zhang and Y. Vorobeychik: Empirically grounded agent-based models of innovation diffusion: a critical review. *Artificial Intelligence Review* 52(1), 707–741 (2019)
19. Y. Zhang, X. Li, M. Aziz-Alaoui, C. Bertelle, J. Guan, and S. Zhou: Knowledge diffusion in complex networks. *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience* 29(3), e3791 (2017)